

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Contours of Communal Idealism in Mahesh Dattani's *Final Solutions*

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ABSTRACT

Dattani's play *Final Solutions* is the true representative play of his observations, dealing with one of the burning issues: communal riot. The play showed how the seed of riot is sown, and some vested groups reap its fruit. Even in the twenty-first century, the concept of idealism makes everyone disgusted with one thing. Because of idealism, many people are suffering in the name of religion. In contemporary society, not only in India but everywhere, a group of people is forced or tortured in the name of terrorism. It is common for everyone to want a good solution to the issue. Idealism is one thing that makes others suffer physically and psychologically. Dattani discusses the roles of politicians, police and the public during a communal riot. The common people who live together for years, at the moment of riot, suddenly cease to recognise one another and become enemies on the grounds of religion. This paper analyses how people's ideology dismantles humanity from their hearts during difficult times and suggests answers to the agony faced by innocents.

Keywords: Ideology, Identity, Final Solutions, Communal Ideology

FULL RESEARCH PAPER**Introduction**

Final Solutions is the fifth play of Mahesh Dattani, which was first performed by Dattani, Preetam Kolipillai and a group at the Guru Nanak Bhawan, Bangalore on July 10, 1993. It was staged just after the Mumbai riot. It is this magnificent work that attracted the critics worldwide, and ultimately, in 1998, he was awarded the 'Sahitya Akademi Award' for his collection of plays, *Final Solutions and Other Plays*. *Final Solutions* is an account of its concentration on one single theme-Hindu-Muslim conflict in the light of rational humanism, is great both as literature and drama. Dattani considers this play as a "turning point in his career as a playwright, it is deeply entrenched in the question of multiple identities that become enmeshed with familial identities, issues that we shall consider elsewhere" (Chaudhuri). The director Alyque Pdamee comments on the play and the issues related to the play in *Collected Plays*, "the demons of communal hatred are not out on the street... they are lurking inside ourselves" (Dattani 161)

Mahesh Dattani demonstrates that the primary cause of the differences engendered by the two leading communities in our country is their sense of superiority. The ideology of being the best makes everyone superior to others. The Hindus always think that they are superior to the Muslim and the Muslim thinks the same. This causes a big chasm in their relationship. Each religious person has their own ideology about other religions. If any group of people crosses the limits of their ideology, it ends in a riot. In this contemporary society, more people are turned into terrorists because of their religion. They are made to follow terrorism by the oppression of other religious people.

Representations of Communal Idealism

Althusser says that Ideology represents the imaginary relationship of individuals to their real conditions of existence (Althusser). The play *Final Solutions* brings out a lot of religious idealism in both religions. All religions believe in the fact that God is the 'Ultimate Reality', but still, hatred and suspicion are spread among different communities. In the very act, people fight but not for food, cloth and shelter, the basic needs of man, but for an abstract thing, religion. A communal riot is like a war, but it is fought not between two nations but between two religious groups. It is an ideological war in which each group wants to show its religion as superior to others. The historian Bipin Chandra, in his work *India's Struggle for Independence*, says, "Communalism is, therefore, basically and above all an ideology on which communal

politics is based" (Chandra 399). So communalism starts with ideological supremacy, and its zenith is the communal riot among different communities of society. He also says that, " communal violence is a conjunctural consequence of communal ideology...Hindu, Muslim, Sikh or Christian communalism are not very different from each other; they belong to a single species; they are varieties of the same communal ideology"(Chandra 399).

Indian drama has explicitly presented the reality of Indian lives and their performances in the works of Indian dramatists. As Naik says, "Indian English drama remained largely a literary rather than a performative art for a long time" (Naik). *Final Solutions* is a play about a family with its simmering undercurrents. Ramnik, the father, transfers his resentment at his own father's black deed to his mother, Hardika. Smita, the daughter, hits out at her mother, Aruna, when she can't cope with her hidden love for Babban, the outsider. Hardika, the grandmother, builds up a hatred for Zarine, her best friend, and her community because she herself can't stand her own in-laws. Aruna, the mother, seems to be the best adjusted, until her daughter shakes her belief in her religion.

In contemporary society, human life is considered the highest value and is given respect. During communal riots, humanity undergoes tremendous spiritual losses, both during and after the riot. Respect for life, dignity of humanity, love for truth and justice, fellow-feeling and brotherhood are mercilessly butchered in riots. People lose not only their bodies but also their souls, all that is true, beautiful and good. It is a great catastrophe for humanity. As Bobby, a character in *Final Solutions*, says,

A minor incident changed all that... we were playing cricket on our street... the postman...was in a hurry and asked Javed to hand the letter over to the owner. Javed took the letter...and opened the gate...a voice boomed, 'What do you want?' Javed holding out the letter...his usual firmness vanishing in a second. 'Leave it on the wall, the voice ordered. Javed backed away, really frightened... the man came out with a cloth... wiped the letter, then picked it up. He then wiped the spot on the wall where the letter was lying, and he wiped the gate! We all heard a continuous ringing of a prayer bell. Not loud. However, distinct...we'd heard the bell so often every day of our lives that it didn't mean anything...but at the moment...we all heard only the bell...The next day...I found...Someone had dropped pieces of meat and bones into his backyard. (Dattani 200)

The first stage of communalism lies in the ideology that the people of the same religion have the same ideology and the same interests. Gatt stresses that "Communal conflict in the play is not merely political but deeply psychological and cultural" (Gatt 127). The vested persons involve themselves in spreading such ideology and dividing the society based on religion. Such a feeling compels the other community to do the same, and thus the cactus of communalism comes to the ground. The ill-treatment of Javed by a man hurts Bobby, and he also becomes angry and expresses his anger to Ramnik. The following conversation between both of them explains,

Ramnik: ...you didn't throw meat into your neighbour's backyard.

Bobby: That's because I was ashamed of being myself. He wasn't.

Ramnik: Ashamed?

Bobby: Yes. Like being apologetic. For being who I was. Moreover, I pretended that I was not a part of my community. For thinking that I could become superior by not belonging...I chose to be called Bobby (Dattani 201).

Bobby opposes communal hatred but follows the communal path to witness the ill-treatment inflicted on his friend. At first, he opposes such an ideology, but he is compelled to follow his community. So it is wrong to call anyone responsible for communal hatred. As Chorus 1 (Muslim) in the play asks some questions related to the form group, "Should we be swallowed up? Until they cannot recognise us? Should we meld into anonymity so that we cannot be hounded? Lose ourselves in a shapeless mass? Should we? Can we? (Dattani 196). The behaviour of Aruna, a female protagonist in the play, closely aligns with this ideology, which holds that she has no ill will toward the other community but that all communities have their own ways of worship. However, all are equal. As she says, "We have nothing against you. It is only that we have our ways and customs and...and...we are all equal... We respect your religion, and we wish you well...All religion is one. Only the ways to God are many" (Dattani 209).

Aruna talks about the age-old Indian tradition that believes in 'Unity in Diversity'. However, Javed is now not in a position to accept the view. The society has brought him to a position to revolt, and he wants to take revenge on the other community for his miseries. It is the last stage of communalism that works as fascists do to impose their ideology. Bipin Chandra calls this 'Extreme Communalism' in *India's Struggle for Independence*, and as he writes,

Extreme communalism was based on fear and hatred and had a tendency to use violence of language, deed or behaviour, the language of war and enmity against political opponents...it was also at this stage that both the Muslim and the Hindu communalists put forward the theory that Muslims and Hindus constituted separate nations whose mutual antagonism was permanent and irresolvable. The Muslim League and the Hindu Mahasabha, after 1937 and Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh (RSS) increasingly veered towards extreme or fascistic communalism (Chandra 399-400).

The play *Final Solutions* also shows that the Police and the Politicians never treat society on equal terms. Politicians whose primary purpose is to gain votes by hook or by crook are often seen indulging in many malpractices. Politicians are the first people who create ideologies in people's minds. We know that in a democratic state, equality is the soul of the nation. In the eyes of the Constitution, all men are equal. They should not be treated based on caste, class and creed with the ideologies in their mind. Shetty thinks that *One India: One People* expresses,

Men are equal. For though they are not of the same age, the same height, the same skin and the same intelligence, these inequalities are temporary and superficial; the soul that is hidden beneath the earthly crust is the same for all men and women belonging to all climes. (Shetty 46)

The most important battle for the Indians in establishing a distinctive identity within a territorial location lay in the partition of India. National identities were conceived and took shape in accordance with the ideologues who formulated them, grounded in religious ideologies. Dattani had actually dramatised it in the form of *Final Solutions* earlier, dealing with the recurring rhetoric of hatred, aggression, the monetary and political exploitation for communal riots, the chauvinism and parochial mindset of the fundamentalist, in the context of India of the 1940s, interspersed with the contemporary India. He subsequently explored the issue of identity, memory, suffering and loss. As Daksha writes her diary in the play,

My father had fought for that hour...He said he was happy we were rid of the Britishers. He also said something I did not understand at the time. He said that before leaving, they had let the dogs loose...However, that night in Hussainabad in our ancestral house- when I heard them outside- I knew that they were thinking the same of us...Moreover, as their voices grew louder, I blamed them more and more for my father's absence. The windows broke, one by one. My mother and I hid in the pooja room. The stones came smashing

into our home. I clung to my mother. My mother clung to the family idol of Lord Krishna...I looked at the idol, I had the most horrible thought...I felt that the idol I had grown up seeing my mother worship was just a painted doll...A stone hit our gramophone table, breaking it. Krishna chose to destroy what I love most. My entire record collection is broken. Lying about like pieces of glass. Shamshed Begun, Noor Jehan, Suraiya...Those beautiful voices. Cracked... (Dattani 167)

The above description is written by Daksha, who, after forty years, sees the same thing repeating before her eyes. The mob of the same sentiment is destroying the harmony of society, as it was shattered in the past. They again forget the language of peace and harmony and seize the opportunity to undermine society's unity by imbibing ideologies about other communities. People still blame the other community for their community's miseries. They do not realise that it is nothing but ideology that will make the same people suffer. As Harthika says, "After forty years... I opened my diary again. And I wrote. A dozen pages before. A dozen pages now. A young girl's childish scribble. An old woman's shaky scrawl. Yes, things have not changed that much" (Dattani 167)

Clothes and dresses can change a person's physical appearance, but the inner soul always remains the same. The real truth is one, and that is God. A person can be a Hindu and a Muslim only by wearing a mask. If he puts off the mask, he can be a real human being. The same man wears the mask of the Hindu; he speaks differently from the Muslim. Dattani has used the mob to show how ideologies were imbibed in one's mind and how some people were forced to become terrorists from the beginning of the partition of India. It's not only an Indian problem; it is an issue worldwide. In a contemporary world, the Muslim community has been treated as terrorists. It was the Americans and the British who created the problem for India and for the world. As Mob speaks,

Chorus 1: The possession has passed through these lanes every year, for forty years!

Chorus 2, 3: How dare they?

Chorus 1, 2, 3: For forty years our chariot has moved through their mohallas.

Chorus 4, 5: Why did they?

Why did they do it today?

Chorus 1: How dare they?

Chorus 2, 3: They broke our rath.

They broke our chariot and felled our Gods!

Chorus 1, 2, 3: This is our land!

How dare they?

Chorus 1: It is in their blood!

Chorus 2, 3: It is in their blood to destroy!

Chorus 4: Why should they?

Chorus 5: It could have been an accident. (Dattani 168)

It is interesting to note that Chorus/Mob is not in favour of accepting any reason behind the event. Dattani used them as the role of the society's idealised thoughts. They only shout mischievous remarks at the other community. They think that for the entire misdeed, only a particular community is responsible. Chorus 5 uses reason, but ultimately his sense is shattered, and others drown out his voice. As Dattani writes, "They repeat their lines till they overlap. Chorus 4 and 5 get more aggressive till these questions become statements. By the end of it, they are an unruly mob crying out for blood" (Dattani 169). Such a feeling does not prevail only among the Mob presenting the Hindus, but also among the Mob representing the Muslims. They talk in the same way. The Muslim chorus speaks,

Chorus 1: Their chariot fell in our street!

Chorus 2: Their God now prostrates before us!

Chorus 3: So they blame it on us?

Chorus 1: Did we build the chariot?

Chorus 2, 3: Blame the builder of those fancy thrones.

Chorus 4: A manufacturing defect!

Chorus 5: Doesn't their God have a warranty?...

Chorus All: We are neither idol makers nor breakers!

Chorus 5: But they blamed it on us!

Chorus All: Why did they? Why did they? Why?

Chorus 5: (emotionally) Why? (Dattani 171)

The mob is nothing, but it represents the people's resentment. They express their feelings that cannot be told individually. Through them, the dramatist depicts the inner feelings and thoughts of the people. The Hindu chorus thinks about the temple, and the Muslim chorus thinks about the mosque. They forget the true spirit of humanity and human religion. Such a type of division is not good for any community. It will be made as an idealised thought in everyone's mind by nature. Moreover, Dattani wants to convey the opposite of what society has led everyone to believe about religion. The Mob typically uses images of animals associated with particular communities. The images of 'pig', 'swine', 'rat', 'lizard', etc., hint at the

communal hatred and contempt toward the other community. It suggests that such arrogant remarks must be stopped in a society that spreads hatred and bitterness. Through these words, Dattani very sincerely depicts the bitterness between the two major groups in the country. The Mob's words are a clear indication of communal disharmony in society and their consequences are felt by the characters Ramnik, Javed, Hardika, Bobby and Zarine's family. Dattani uses the chorus in the play to reveal the true, idealised minds of both communities.

Tackling the issue with ease

The play offers palpable solutions. At the beginning, Chorus 1 declares, "A drop of oil cannot merge with an ocean of milk. One reality cannot accept another reality" (Dattani 196). Here, the speaker represents the Muslim community and pines for its identity. He emphasises that no one can deny the reality that Muslims are citizens of India and they should be given their due share. At last, the representative of the Muslim mob, Bobby, puts the image of Lord Krishna in his hand and says, "Your God! My flesh is holding Him! Look Javed! And He does not mind!" (Dattani 216). Even the chorus representing the Muslim community speaks thrice, "We are not idol breakers" (Dattani 224)

This is an interesting solution in which the God of a community does not find any trouble in the hands of another community. It shows that the division of the community and the creation of different gods are the gifts of society, and so mutual understanding should be maintained. Moreover, he undermines the play's ideology. The concept of ideology, which is stored in the mind, has been erased by this solution. Then the society will not feel any harm, and the fabric of society can be maintained. The pride of all will be great. As Bobby says, "See, Javed! He doesn't humiliate you. He doesn't cringe from my touch. He welcomes the warmth of my hand. He feels me. Moreover, He welcomes it! I hold Him who is sacred to them, but I do not commit sacrilege" (Dattani 224).

Conclusion

Dattani presents an ideal view: God does not discriminate, but it is man who thinks otherwise. God is one, but there are many paths to reach Him. One may call Him-Ram, Rahim, Christ, etc. However, he is one. Bobby again gives a philosophical view, "I don't believe in Him, but He believes in me. He smiles. He smiles at our trivial pride and our trivial shame" (Dattani 224). Dattani, the dramatist, has a dream of unity of both the communities –the Hindu and the Muslim. His primary purpose in the play is to maintain a workable unity and co-operation between these two leading

communities of India. He does not want to see his nation be separated in the name of ideology. In this respect, he seems to be very much influenced by late Sadananda A. Shetty, the founder editor of the *'One India: One People'*, who observes in his poem *Who am I*,

Am I a Hindu first or an Indian first?
Am I a Muslim first or an Indian first?
Am I a Christian first or an Indian first?
Am I a Buddhist first or an Indian first?
Am I a Brahmin first or an Indian first?
Am I a Dalit first or an Indian first?
Am I a South Indian first or an Indian first?
Am I a North Indian first or an Indian first?
Am I the President of India first or an Indian first?
Am I the Prime Minister of India first or an Indian first?
Am I the commander-in- chief first or an Indian first?
Am I a supporter of only 'ism' first or an Indian first?
Am I a white-collar/blue-collar worker first or an Indian first?
Am I a youth/senior citizen first, or an Indian first?
In all cases, you are Indian First, Last and Always.
Be a proud Indian. Make this country Great, Strong and United. (Shetty 11/ 1)

To sum up, Dattani, through the play *Final Solutions*, explores the issues of identity, memory, suffering and loss and the resulting 'other-bashing', using either/or terms within the larger political context through the various products of idealism in this play. As Devi portrays, "The crisis within the family in Dattani's plays is both psychological and social, exposing the fragility of human relationships" (Devi). He, through this beautiful, realistic presentation of two major groups of India, has tried his best to provide a workable solution to fill the gap between the Hindus and the Muslims. He seems very certain about protecting his vision of secularism, in which both communities live together in harmony.

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